

Therapy-induced transcriptome variations to promote heart cell senescence reversal

Version 1

Description

We investigate changes in gene transcription caused by current and potential medications on senescent heart cells to model their potential use in senescence reversal. The model involves medication-induced changes in gene expression levels to observe dose-dependent and combined effects on transcriptomes. Initial models are created by analysing standardized cell lines and validated in patient samples to assess their relevance to real-life scenarios.

Funder

Central Finance and Contracting Agency

Grant

Investigation of therapy-induced transcriptome variations to promote cardiomyocyte senescence reversal (17/BMC/PG)

Researchers

Kaspars Megnis (orcid:0000-0002-2587-9272)

Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Therapy-induced transcriptome variations to promote heart cell senescence reversal](#)

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Researchers:

[Kaspars Megnis \(orcid:0000-0002-2587-9272\)](#)

Organizations:

[Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Central Finance and Contracting Agency](#)

Grants: [Investigation of therapy-induced transcriptome variations to promote cardiomyocyte senescence reversal \(17/BMC/PG\)](#)

Project: [Cite Project](#)

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

It describes the planned use of data in the project.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

During the study, transcriptome sequencing data is collected, as well as notes on visual observations regarding the response of cells to the presence of various substances. Data are collected to determine the effect of certain test substances on cardiomyocyte senescence during subsequent analysis.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- Others

Sequencing data will be collected in FASTQ format

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The research is based on and uses data from our unique experiments. If in the future, as a result of some collaboration, it becomes possible to compare them with data from other researchers in similar experiments, then this will be done. However, this is not the primary goal for now.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

For researchers conducting similar experiments.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Data Package

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

cardiomyocytes, senescence, transcriptome

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

ArrayExpress / BioStudies platforma (EMBL-EBI)

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/>

I will use the ArrayExpress / BioStudies platform (EMBL-EBI) because it is widely recommended for storing both raw and processed transcriptomic data in European-funded research projects. It ensures compliance with FAIR data principles and provides seamless integration with ENA for raw sequencing files. The platform is free to use and allows comprehensive metadata annotation, enhancing data discoverability and long-term accessibility.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data from the ArrayExpress / BioStudies platform can be accessed through a user-friendly web interface, which allows browsing, viewing metadata, and downloading raw and processed files. After downloading, the data can be viewed and used with a PDF reader, BASH command lines, R (Bioconductor packages) or wide variety of other tools, based on researchers personal preferences.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

The tools available for further use of data are constantly changing and evolving, and different researchers have different specific preferences in this area. Therefore, we rely on the researchers' own expertise in choosing the tools.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

PDF - PDF reader

FASTQ - BASH or R

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

CC0 1.0

The data will be licensed under the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal (Public Domain Dedication) license, to ensure unrestricted reuse, redistribution, and integration into future research. This approach supports open science and complies with FAIR data principles.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-03

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-01-03

The date given is only a very rough estimate. We intend to keep data reusable as long as possible.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Certain data quality marks are included in the data itself.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

We will use free solutions whenever possible.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Kaspars Megnis (orcid: [0000-0002-2587-9272](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2587-9272))

Kaspars Megnis will lead data management and, when necessary, will attract local experts from among colleagues and partners.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

After the end of this particular project, it is planned to continue this research topic by attracting funding from new projects.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

- Other

Data will be stored and shared using secure, trusted public repositories such as ENA and BioStudies (EMBL-EBI), which maintain robust infrastructure, data integrity safeguards, and controlled access options during embargo periods. All data will be anonymized and checked for compliance with ethical standards before submission. No personal or sensitive information will be included, and all procedures will adhere to applicable data protection regulations, including GDPR where relevant.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Cell cultures obtained from clinic patients may be used at the end of the study.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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